

Joint statement on the European Research Area Act

Ensuring a researcher-centred European Research Area

Submitted on behalf of representatives of the European Research Area (ERA) Forum Stakeholder Group 4: Association of ERC Grantees (AERG), The Council of European Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc), Initiative for Science in Europe (ISE), and the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA).

The representatives of the ERA Forum Stakeholder Group 4 welcome the European Commission's initiative to introduce the ERA Act as a timely and necessary step to strengthen Europe's research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem, reduce fragmentation, and enhance the European Union (EU)'s global competitiveness. We underline the central role of the ERA Forum as a key platform for coordination, mutual learning, and inclusive governance. Meaningful and systematic stakeholder engagement is essential for the legitimacy, effectiveness, and long-term success of the ERA Act. We support the objective of creating a more coherent, attractive, and resilient ERA, grounded in shared values, sustainable investment, and strong framework conditions for research and researchers.

Sustained public investment in R&I is a fundamental prerequisite for achieving the ERA's objectives. The persistent gap in research and development (R&D) intensity between the EU and other global leaders continues to undermine Europe's competitiveness, societal resilience, and capacity to attract and retain talent. Reaching the long-standing target of 3% of gross domestic product (GDP) invested in R&D, corresponding to an estimated €220 billion per year, requires binding and transparent public commitments by Member States, with at least 1–1.25% GDP dedicated to public R&D investment. EU-level legislation can play a decisive role by establishing enforceable national investment targets, supported by multiannual roadmaps, monitoring, and accountability mechanisms. Public R&D funding must remain the backbone of the system, complemented, but not replaced, by private investment, particularly to sustain frontier, fundamental, and investigator-driven research.

Greater **alignment of R&I policies, investments and programmes** across the EU and Member States is essential to reduce fragmentation and improve efficiency. Such alignment should focus on the coherence of framework conditions, governance, and interoperability, rather than on increased directionality of research agendas. Europe's long-term strength depends on a balanced research ecosystem that safeguards independent, excellence-based, and bottom-up funding instruments. In this context, the autonomy and non-directional, bottom-up nature of programmes such as the **Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA)** and the **European Research Council (ERC)** must be explicitly protected, as they are proven drivers of talent development, mobility, interdisciplinarity, and global scientific excellence.

Improving the **general conditions for research and researchers in Europe** must be a core pillar of the ERA Act. **Freedom of scientific research** is a foundational value of the ERA and a prerequisite for innovation, democratic resilience, and public trust in science. However, its protection remains uneven across the EU and is increasingly challenged by political, economic, and structural pressures. The ERA Act should therefore provide a clear and enforceable framework for safeguarding academic freedom, institutional autonomy, and transparent governance. The establishment of an independent European ombudsperson for academic freedom would provide a dedicated mechanism to support researchers, monitor compliance, and help address systemic risks.

Gender equality and equal opportunities are integral to research excellence and societal relevance. While EU-level measures such as Gender Equality Plans have driven progress, implementation remains uneven. The ERA Act should reinforce minimum standards while allowing flexibility in implementation, and promote evidence-based approaches that address structural barriers, including support for researchers with caregiving responsibilities. Successful models, including the MSCA, demonstrate that well-designed programmes can effectively promote inclusiveness and balanced participation.

Attractive and sustainable **research careers and mobility** are essential for the free circulation of knowledge and talent within the ERA. Persistent precarity, widespread use of fixed-term contracts, limited social security coverage, and complex administrative and visa procedures continue to undermine Europe's attractiveness - particularly for early-career and third-country national researchers. The ERA Act should set minimum standards for research employment, ensuring that researchers funded through EU programmes, including doctoral candidates and postdoctoral researchers, are employed under transparent contracts with full access to social security. The EU should set clear conditions for the use of researcher funding and bind minimum requirements for EU-funded positions, similar to existing eligibility criteria. This would support upward convergence across Member States and enable necessary national reforms.

The **free circulation of scientific knowledge** is a cornerstone of the ERA. The ERA Act should consolidate and reinforce existing commitments to open science in all its dimensions, including open access to publications supported by secondary publishing rights and sustainable publishing platforms, such as Open Research Europe. These efforts must be complemented by continued commitments to research data management and investments in trusted open infrastructures. Reforms in research assessment are an essential step to recognise quality, openness, and the full diversity of researcher contributions, while also enabling equitable access to knowledge across the ERA.

Finally, **knowledge valorisation** should be supported through balanced and inclusive approaches that recognise a broad range of research contributions beyond commercialisation alone. Aligning reward and assessment systems, strengthening institutional support structures, and facilitating purposeful intersectoral mobility are key to ensuring that publicly funded research delivers societal, economic, and policy value.

In conclusion, we encourage the European Commission to use the ERA Act to reinforce shared values, sustainable investment, and coherent framework conditions across Europe. By safeguarding academic freedom, strengthening public R&D investment, protecting excellence-based programmes, and improving research careers and mobility, the ERA Act can significantly enhance Europe's capacity to generate knowledge, innovation, and societal impact for the benefit of all.

About organizations endorsing this statement

The Association of ERC Grantees (AERG) is an independent international non-profit organization operating under Belgian Law and governed by its membership. The AERG builds on the success of the ERC grant programme and is aligned on the common objectives of promoting excellent science within Europe on a bottom-up principle, and of demonstrating the wider societal benefits of funding excellent, high-risk, high-gain scientific research.

The Initiative for Science in Europe (ISE) is an independent platform of European Learned Societies and Research Organizations supporting all fields of science at a European level to engage in European science strategies and policies.

The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc), is a grassroots federation of 28 national associations of early-career researchers (ECRs) from 25 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) is a global network of researchers who benefit or have benefited from the Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions (MSCA). The MCAA supports and contributes to the advancement of knowledge for a global, diverse, and informed society. The main focus of the MCAA is to promote career development and offer networking opportunities to its members, and contribute to shaping research and innovation policy. The MCAA currently has over 24,000 members from more than 150 countries, representing all career stages and diverse research fields. MCAA has over 35 geographical Chapters and more than 10 thematic Working Groups.